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1. Introduction

The LEAPS-INNOV partners have been working on six collaborative technology projects (work packages WP2-7) selected from the LEAPS Technology Roadmap (<https://www.leaps-initiative.eu/technology-development/>) based on their innovation potential and their ability to advance and maintain European light source leadership.

The LEAPS-INNOV project was focused in developing the interaction and partnership of the LEAPS facilities with industry in two key aspects:

- Firstly, with industry as a collaborator in technological developments (WP2-7): LEAPS is a very strong and highly innovative player for high-end technology industry in Europe and worldwide, which are often SMEs, where companies serve as suppliers to the facilities of beyond state-of-the-art technologies they need to stay at the forefront of science (national investments of approximately EUR 2.3 billion for approved and planned upgrades of LEAPS RIs from 2020 to 2030, and additional investments from over 30 non-European facilities). The LEAPS facilities are therefore willing and able to take significant technological risks together with the industrial partners to incorporate cutting-edge technologies into their facility portfolios and to enable the industrial partners to gain an edge in technology supply. A detailed Exploitation Plan (Table 1) has been developed to guide the activities of WP2-7.
- Secondly, with industry as a user of the facilities (WP8): All facilities strive to have industry exploiting their facilities as users, demonstrating direct economic relevance and support to industry by providing high quality services. SMEs remain under-represented in this aspect and, based upon the successful activities within the Horizon 2020 project CALIPSOplus, a single access portal programme targeting SMEs as users depicts one key part of the industry relations that LEAPS-INNOV is targeting. This development is in line with standardisation and harmonisation of processes at RIs, a key issue for industrial users seeking research infrastructures. In terms of facility use, and where Europe has the world-leading set of light sources, LEAPS-INNOV will build a medium- and long-term perspective on enhanced engagement, using the critical mass of LEAPS and the vast pool of expertise, tools and scientific know-how for supporting industry. This will allow LEAPS to look and act ahead in concrete terms for smarter and deeper connections with the European industry base.

Table 1: Exploitation Plan

#WP	Exploitable technology (Deliverable)	Application Sector or end user	Core Exploitation Channel	Expected Impact	IPR Measures	Timeline for Exploitation	Further R&D Needed
WP2 -XAFS- DEF	Multi-Channel Integrated preamplifier (D 2.2)	Detector Industry in Europe	Subcontracting Company	Higher Performance Detector Systems		2 years after end of the project	
	Germanium Detector (D2.4)	Detector Industry and XAFS beamlines worldwide	Production Plan made available to commercial producer, industrial workshop	High throughput and performance of XAFS beamlines worldwide	Licence of Patent	2 years after end of the project	Extension of number of detector channels
WP3 - SUPERFLAT	Metrology Techniques (D3.3)	Optics suppliers and metrology laboratories in Europe	Dissemination to industry and all photon sources	Improved optics manufacture	License	5-7 years after end of the project	
	Higher Quality Mirrors with improved figure errors (D3.4)	High Performance X-Ray SR and FEL beamlines worldwide	PCP	Higher photon intensities, smaller spatial resolution, reduced wave front perturbation; less dependency on single company worldwide	https://leaps-superflat.eu/pcp-questions-answers/	5-7 years after end of the project	Extension of Processing to larger mirrors
WP4 - NeXtgrating	Grating using electron-beam lithography (EBL) fabrication process (D4.4)	Soft X-Ray SR and FEL beamlines laser laboratories worldwide	Spin-out and start up	Higher Performance soft X-Ray beamlines	License or Patent	5-7 years after end of the project	EBL Processes for large gratings
WP5 - POSIT	Magnetic Levitation stage demonstrator (D 5.5)	Soft X-Ray SR and FEL beamlines laser laboratories worldwide				2 years after end of the project	
	Microfluidic chip (D5.6)	Structural Analysis Beamlines			License or Patent	2 years after end of the project	
	Synchronization demonstrator (D5.7)	Short-pulse SR and FEL beamlines in Europe	Dissemination to industry and all photon sources	Higher Time resolution at short-pulse beamlines	Open Source	2 years after end of the project	
WP6 - LIDS	Measurement benches (D 6.3)	Undulator labs & commercial suppliers in Europe			License or Patent	2 years after end of the project	
	Short Period high field undulators (D6.4)	High Performance X-Ray SR and FEL beamlines worldwide	Dissemination to industry and all photon sources	Higher spectral brilliance in soft and hard X-ray range at SR, FEL and compact sources	License or Patent	5-7 years after end of the project	
	Advanced EPU undulators (D 6.5)				License or Patent	5-7 years after end of the project	
WP7 - DATA	Data reduction and compression protocols (D 7.4)	High Performance X-Ray SR and FEL beamlines worldwide	Dissemination to industry and all photon sources	More cost effective, resource efficient data treatment	Open Source	2 years after end of the project	

WP8 has been designed around the specific objective to “Create an innovation ecosystem around light sources” which covers, amongst other activities, the two aspects mentioned above.

The role of WP8 has been to coordinate bridging toward industry as a technology collaborator supporting the technology developments WP2-7, as well as facilitating the transfer of LEAPS skills, technology and know-how towards industry (also as technology user) and the economy at an accelerated level via the following tasks:

- Building partnerships with industry in its role as user, collaborator and supplier of LEAPS facilities across the EU member states, including industry-targeted events

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- Exchanging best practices, including IPR rules, and building collaborative and joint approaches towards industry
- Supporting the activities of the RI Open Innovation Coordination Group of the Innovation Pilots
- Facilitating access for SMEs via a dedicated platform to promote cutting-edge industrial research at LEAPS facilities.

This document is focused on the work done under Task 8.1.1: Light source exploitation and under Task 8.2: Boost innovation in European SMEs. Through these tasks, involving all LEAPS members, the WP8 representatives are supporting the beneficiaries of those WPs with industry engagement, intellectual property, and/or technology transfer issues to exploit their results in the most appropriate way and has been done in close concert with the WP teams. Task 8.2 strengthen the bridges between SMEs and light sources through a dedicated programme, named TamaTA-INNOV, that provided subsidised access for SMEs to the facilities.

The document summarises the activities done to support the WPs in their developments and an overall outcome of TamaTA-INNOV programme.

2. Task 8.1.1.: Light sources technology exploitation

2.1 Methodology

Close monitoring of the activities was implemented during the reporting period with the aim of supporting the beneficiaries of the technical WPs (WP2-WP7) with industry engagement, intellectual property, and/or technology transfer issues.

A representative of WP8 was been assigned to each WP (Table 2).

Table 2: Representative of WP8 Assigned to WP 2-7

#	Title	Contact Person
WP2	High throughput X-ray spectroscopy detector system	Stefan Mueller, PSI
WP3	High performance X-ray mirror and grating substrate	Ed Mitchell, ESRF
WP4	Next generation of X-ray diffraction gratings	Elizabeth Shotton, Diamond
WP5	New positioning and scanning systems for speed and accuracy	Alejandro Sanchez, ALBA
WP6	Insertion Devices	Antonio Bonucci, XFEL -Marco Peloi; Elettra
WP7	Data Reduction and Compression	Magnus Larsson; MAXIV

The questionnaire, developed by ALBA-CELLS and ELETTRA named “Light Sources Exploitation Questionnaire” (Figure 1) is composed by a set of questions divided into three main sections (Figure 1).

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Figure 1: “Light Sources Exploitation Questionnaire”

The WP8 representatives participated in the WP2-7 technical meeting during the LEAPS-INNOV Annual Meetings in 2022, 2023, 2024 and 2025 to gather further information about industrial involvement and know-how development. This information has been shared in the WP8 meeting and included in the updates of exploitation for WP2-7.

- “Annual Meetings”: WP8 representatives participated in the WP2-7 technical meeting during the LEAPS-INNOV Annual Meetings to gather further information about industrial involvement and know-how development.
- “Project Review meetings” have provided the opportunity to collect more information about the status of the activities
- “Light Sources Exploitation Questionnaire”: The WP leaders of WP2-7 were contacted by a representative of WP8 with the request to fill a questionnaire. The request was sent in 2021 and again in December 2022 and January 2023 to collect further updates of the progress of the activities.

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- Direct surveys and discussions with WP leaders: a representative of WP8 was assigned to technical WP as a reference point for feedback and monitoring

2.2 Summary of results

The “Light Sources Exploitation Questionnaire” was completed by the WP leaders of

- WP2- XAFS -DET (High throughout X-ray spectroscopy detector system)
- WP3 - SuperFlat (High performance X-ray mirror and grating substrate)
- WP4 - NeXtgrating (Next generation of X-ray diffraction gratings)
- WP5 - POSIT (New positioning and scanning systems for speed and accuracy)
- WP6 - LIDs (Insertion Devices)
- WP7 - DATA (Data Reduction and Compression)

with the assistance of the representatives of WP8 (PSI, ESRF, DIAMOND, ULUND, ALBA-CELLS, ELETTRA and EuXFEL). Moreover, additional meeting with the WP leaders and participation in other discussion forums, such as the annual meetings gave the opportunity to collect more information about the status of the activities.

The technological needs were clearly identified from the beginning, with a strong emphasis on the requirements of facilities to support development and implementation. These requirements were detailed in the project deliverables, ensuring a structured approach and shared understanding among stakeholders. However, it was acknowledged that these initial specifications might evolve following engagement with industrial partners, as their input could lead to adjustments based on practical feasibility, market demands, or production constraints. Indeed, the validation of technical requirements defined at the experimental level in a real production process was often challenging to attain.

The intellectual property (IP) protection strategy was not clearly defined at the outset, except in cases where it was explicitly addressed within public tender procedures. This lack of predefined strategy highlighted later a broader need for support and guidance in managing IP issues to exploit the know-how. Numerous WP participants expressed the need for dedicated training on intellectual property rights (IPR), underscoring a general gap in knowledge and preparedness in this area. To address these challenges, assistance from Industrial Contact Offices (ICOs), and legal experts was identified as essential to ensure that IP generated during collaborations is properly managed, protected, and aligned with both institutional policies and industry expectations.

The strategy for industrial involvement benefited from the fact that industrial contacts were relatively easy to establish, as most of the relevant companies were already well-known within the field. This existing familiarity facilitated initial engagement and

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accelerated the formation of collaborative relationships. Despite this, some companies were not able to deliver the required solutions or meet the technical specifications, highlighting the need for careful assessment of industrial capabilities during partner selection as well as a deeper knowledge of the market. As a result, the strategy evolved over time, adapting to the specific needs of the project, feedback from partners, and the shifting landscape of technological and commercial priorities.

Overall, the companies involved in the activities of the WP2-7 totalled 56, 46% of which are SMEs (see Figure 2) in Europe (see Figure 3). Several informal company consultations have not been included in these numbers as no records are present in project documentation.

Figure 2: Percentage of companies involved divided by size

Figure 3: Geographic Distribution of companies involved in the activities

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Figure 4: Means of Involvement (%)

Figure 5: Means of Involvement of SME and LARGE companies (No. of Companies)

The companies have been involved in the activities of WP2-7 in several different ways (see Figure 4 and 5) including participation in dedicated workshops (WP6 mainly) and other procurement procedures (call for tenders, competitive dialogue and PCP). Several companies have been actively involved in the project from its early stages, with some participating as official partners from the beginning. On average, each work package (WP) engaged around three companies, ensuring a consistent and meaningful industrial contribution across all areas. The procurement procedures successfully included a mix of both small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and large companies, reflecting a broad and inclusive approach to industrial collaboration. Furthermore, dissemination activities were an integral part of the strategy, featuring targeted workshops and dedicated meetings at major events such as BSBF2022, IPAC2024 and BSBF2024, which helped to share results, strengthen partnerships, and attract wider interest from the industrial community.

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2.3 Feedback, Challenges and Lessons Learned

The project activities clearly demonstrated that collaboration with industry is essential for Research Infrastructures (RIs) to successfully develop new technologies.

Industry provides valuable expertise in engineering, manufacturing, and market-driven innovation that complements the scientific knowledge of research institutions. By working together, both sectors can accelerate the transition from research to application, ensuring that technologies are not only technically sound but also scalable and commercially viable. Moreover, industry partnerships help align technological developments with real-world needs, improve access to specialized equipment and skills, and open new opportunities for funding and exploitation of results. This synergy is key to fostering innovation with tangible societal and economic impact.

The collaboration between Industry and Research Infrastructures (RIs) has proven to be mutually beneficial, particularly in projects requiring multiple rounds of testing and validation. In such cases, the combination of tools, technologies, and specialized knowledge possessed by each partner enabled the successful verification of functionalities and accelerated problem-solving. Both parties brought complementary expertise to the table—while RIs contributed deep scientific understanding and advanced research capabilities, industry partners offered practical engineering experience and manufacturing know-how. This synergy not only improved the overall quality and feasibility of the technological developments but also allowed all stakeholders to grow their skills in structured project documentation and process management.

One of the added benefits for industrial partners was the potential for generating revenue through royalties or licensing agreements based on the know-how developed during the collaboration. This provided a clear incentive for active participation and long-term engagement. However, to fully capitalize on these opportunities, there is a need to have the involvement of Industrial Contact Offices (ICOs) from the beginning.

Notably, the most successful outcomes were achieved when industry partners were involved from the very beginning of the project. Early engagement helped to overcome technical and organizational challenges more efficiently and ensured that developments were aligned with both research objectives and market needs. Again, the involvement of Industrial Contact Offices (ICOs) from the start of the work packages (WPs) was critical to streamline communication, manage intellectual property issues, and ensure that the innovations developed were positioned for real-world application and potential commercialization.

The feedback collected from the experience of technical WPs teams in working with industry during the project has been organized into the following topics.

a. Objectives & Priorities

Research infrastructures focus on knowledge generation, while industries prioritize profitability and market competitiveness: research infrastructures are primarily dedicated to advancing knowledge, fostering innovation, and supporting scientific discovery, often driven by long-term societal and academic goals. They serve as the foundation for generating new insights, developing technologies, and training skilled personnel, typically without immediate concern for commercial returns. In contrast, industries operate within competitive markets where profitability, efficiency and customer demands guide decision-making. While they may leverage research outputs, their investments are often directed toward solutions with clear economic value and market potential. Despite these differing priorities, collaboration between research infrastructures and industry can drive both scientific progress and economic growth.

Technical Specifications coming from experimental requirements are challenging to attain for industrial producers: technical specifications derived from experimental requirements often present significant challenges for industrial producers, as they typically demand levels of precision, customization, or innovation that exceed standard manufacturing capabilities. These specifications are driven by scientific goals rather than cost-efficiency, requiring materials, components, or systems that may not yet exist in the commercial market or that push the limits of current technology. Meeting such demands can involve complex design iterations, high development costs, and the need for specialized expertise or equipment. As a result, industrial producers must balance these technical challenges with practical considerations like scalability, reliability, and economic viability, making close collaboration with researchers essential to bridge the gap between experimental ambition and industrial realization.

Specification and needs must be written and clearly defined: clearly written and well-defined specifications and needs are essential for the success of any collaborative project, particularly those involving complex technical or scientific goals. They serve as a common reference point for all stakeholders, ensuring that expectations, performance criteria, and constraints are understood and agreed upon from the outset. This clarity helps prevent miscommunication, reduces the risk of costly redesigns or delays, and enables industrial partners to assess feasibility, allocate resources effectively, and plan production accordingly. Moreover, precise specifications support better quality control, facilitate compliance with standards, and provide a solid foundation for innovation by outlining the exact requirements that solutions must meet.

b. Regulatory, Compliance & IP

When dealing with specific public purchasing procedures some delays occur and many different expertise need to be involved: when dealing with specific public purchasing procedures, delays are a common challenge due to the complexity and formality of the processes involved. These procedures often require strict compliance with legal and regulatory frameworks, which can be time-consuming and rigid. Additionally, they necessitate the involvement of multiple experts from various fields, including legal advisors, financial officers, technical specialists, and procurement professionals. Coordinating input from these diverse areas can slow down decision-making but is essential to ensure transparency, accountability, and adherence to public sector standards. As a result, while public procurement aims to ensure fairness and value for money, it often introduces significant administrative overhead and extended timelines.

Validation of metrology protocols and manufacturing processes (standardization!): in the collaboration between companies and public research infrastructures, the validation of metrology protocols and manufacturing processes plays a critical role in ensuring reliability, reproducibility, and compatibility across innovations. Establishing standardized procedures allows both parties to align on measurement accuracy, quality control, and production consistency—key elements for scaling up experimental results into industrial applications. Standardization also facilitates regulatory approval, market acceptance, and interoperability between components or systems developed by different entities. By jointly validating these protocols, companies gain confidence in product performance, while research infrastructures ensure that their developments are transferable and impactful beyond the lab. This shared effort strengthens the bridge between scientific advancement and industrial competitiveness.

Need to clarify disclosure rules on ownership, use, and commercialization of research outcomes: clarifying disclosure rules on the ownership, use, and commercialization of research outcomes is essential to foster transparency, trust, and effective collaboration among research institutions, industry partners, and funding bodies. Ambiguities in these rules can lead to disputes over intellectual property rights, hinder the practical application of research findings, and discourage investment from commercial stakeholders. Clearly defined guidelines help ensure that all parties understand their rights and obligations from the outset, support the fair distribution of benefits, and promote responsible innovation. Moreover, such clarity enhances compliance with legal and ethical standards, ultimately contributing to more efficient knowledge transfer and the successful translation of research into societal and economic value.

c. Market Situation

Working with industry means also to have to deal with current market (&political) situation: the current market landscape is characterized by a limited number of players, which poses significant challenges in terms of flexibility and supply chain resilience. This scarcity often leads to delays that stem from supplier-related issues, many of which are difficult to anticipate in advance. Common problems include the unavailability of critical parts, extended timelines for testing, and unexpected failures during the testing phase. These factors can significantly impact project schedules and budget planning, particularly in highly specialized sectors where alternative suppliers are rare or non-existent.

d. Cultural & Communication Gaps

Differences in working culture, pace and language (academic vs. business) hinder smooth collaboration: collaboration between industry and research infrastructures often encounters cultural and communication gaps that can hinder project efficiency and mutual understanding. One key challenge is the need to involve the entire research team from the beginning while maintaining frequent and open interaction with the company's team. Without this inclusive and ongoing dialogue, important details can be overlooked, leading to delays or misaligned expectations. Equally important is the clear and precise definition of specifications and needs. Vague or evolving requirements often lead to misunderstandings, conflicting assumptions, and rework. Bridging these gaps requires a structured communication strategy, mutual respect for different working cultures, and a shared commitment to transparency and collaboration throughout the project lifecycle.

3. Task 8.2.: Boost Innovation in European SMEs

3.1. Introduction

Boost innovation in European SMEs (Task 8.2), named TamaTA-INNOV, aims to enhance a pre-existing centralised service for SMEs in Europe based on a specific access system, having a procedure as light as possible, and where industry applications for service will be submitted to a central entry point for all the partners and be evaluated remotely and rapidly by an independent selection panel of experts.

The access scheme is based on the previous pilot programme TamaTA developed within the CALIPSOplus European project by updating it with the lessons learnt in that programme.

This Deliverable D8.5 is presenting the procedure established for TamaTA-INNOV programme, the outreach activities to reach out SMEs within the project, is reporting the proposals received during the calls, feedback from the companies and summarise the outcome of the programme and future perspectives to enhance the innovation impact for light sources in collaboration with SMEs.

3.2. TamaTA-INNOV procedure

The procedure for the TamaTA-INNOV programme has been established by ALBA-CELLS and ELETTRA. The SMEs could apply for subsidised access to the following European light sources: ALBA, DESY, DIAMOND, ELETTRA, ESRF, EuXFEL, FELIX, HZB, INFN, MAX-IV, PSI and SOLEIL. Although not initially involved in this Task, the scheme was also open to the rest of partners of WP8: ISA, SOLARIS, PTB, HZDR and KIT.

The established procedure (Figure 6) was based on a call for proposals system centralised in a single-entry point (<https://wfl.elettra.eu/tamata/>) where the company had to fill in a short description of the project, the samples they would like to be measured, as well as the anticipated innovation and impact. The proposals were technically evaluated by the selected facility and sent to two different reviewers for external evaluation. For this, a list of 10 reviewers was nominated with different fields of expertise. Calls for proposals for SMEs to apply were launched periodically although the evaluation process took place in a continuous way upon the receipt of proposals. If a proposal was approved, the access to the facility was then formalised (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Flow diagram of the SME access through TamaTA-INNOV

The terms of references applicable to this programme were defined according to the European research and development framework regulations and the company had to accept them before submitting a proposal (Annex II). In addition, TamaTA-INNOV coordinators recorded a list of documents with the aim to register and to follow-up each proposal and experiment (Annex III).

3.3. Analysis of the TamaTA-INNOV proposals

In total, 4 calls for proposals were launched and completed (Table 3, Figure 7) although they were rolling calls since the evaluation process takes place on an continuous basis right after the industrial proposals are received.

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Table 3. Call for proposal schedule

Call	Starting date	Ending date	Comments
1	November 11, 2021	July 31, 2022	
2	September 9, 2022	July 28, 2023	Two extra fields added in the application form (company webpage and postal address)
3	September 14, 2023	July 24, 2024	
4	September 12, 2024	May 30, 2025	Call extended as the project extended for 6 months

Figure 7: Partial view of the on-line application form (<https://wfl.elettra.eu/tamata/>)

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INFO & CONTACTS BEFORE SUBMITTING A PROPOSAL

CALL FOR SMEs PROPOSALS

The current call is open from Sep 9, 2022 to Jul 28, 2023

Personal information

Last name
Last name

First name
First name

Email
Email

Confirm Email
Confirm Email

SME information

Company name
Company name

Company webpage
Company webpage

Company postal address
Company postal address

I confirm that my company is a SME according to EU definition (<https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes/sme-definition>)

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INFO & CONTACTS BEFORE SUBMITTING A PROPOSAL

CALL FOR SMEs PROPOSALS

The current call has been extended until May 30, 2025

Personal information

Last name
Last name

First name
First name

Email
Email

Confirm Email
Confirm Email

SME information

Company name
Company name

Company webpage
Company webpage

Company postal address
Company postal address

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A total of 32 SME proposals were received through the single entry point requesting 38 different accesses. Call 1 closed with 8 proposals, call 2 with 16, call 3 with 7 and call 4 with 1. Several proposals requested access to more than one facility (Figure 8). One of the advantages of TamaTA-INNOV programme is that SMEs can have subsidised access to light sources through a very easy and agile process and one company may have access to more than one single facility by submitting just one proposal requesting a complete service to several facilities. This has been shown to be very useful as there are three different companies that have applied for service at different facilities with the same proposal. The first one, had access to ESRF, DESY, SLS, Soleil and ALBA to study a new methodology to characterise drugs using powder diffraction; in the other two, the companies requested beamtime at the ESRF and MAXIV with PSI analysing the data for the company. These are different examples on how light sources have complementary capabilities and how a single entry point facilitates the paperwork and access to the SMEs.

Figure 8: Number of proposals and accesses per call and facility

The proposals received are from companies coming from 14 different countries, most of them from Europe and one from USA, showing that the European light sources services are also appealing for companies from non-European countries (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Number of proposals per SME country

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Given the multidisciplinary nature of the light source techniques, the industrial sectors of the proposals are very diverse, being the most common additive manufacturing, health and cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and instrumentation (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Number of proposals per industrial sector

Other aspects of the proposals received have been analysed to have a deeper knowledge of the importance of the projects received. One of these aspects is the analysis of the impact that the research project and the characterisation performed in light sources may have in terms of material and product development, and performance. Results show that most of the projects were related to new product, material or service development and product improvement. Other important aspects addressed included battery technology development and product and service performance claims (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Number of proposals per type of impact

Another index very relevant for industries is the TRL, technology readiness level, which gives an idea on how close a product or service is to the market. The TRL level of the TamaTA-INNOV proposals were analysed in order to know the starting TRL and the expected TRL at the end of the project. This information is very useful to better understand how the light sources techniques can help in the commercialisation progress (Figure 12).

Figure 12. TRL before the light source access and TRL expected after the performance of the proposal (26 out of 32 proposals have provided this information).

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Results show that the starting TRLs are very different in each project, from a minimum of TRL 1 up to TRL 9. Also, the expectations of most of the projects is to increase the TRL after the experiment. It shows that first, light source techniques may contribute to many different steps and second, may contribute to approaching the product or technology to the market.

From the 32 proposals received, all of them completed the full evaluation process: all of them had the technical feasibility approved and only one failed at the external review stage and was not granted. In only one proposal there was a disagreement between reviewers. In such cases, the proposal was submitted to a third reviewer for final evaluation. In addition, five of the projects were rejected for various reasons such as the company not fulfilling the SME requirements, the service not available at the facility, company lost interest etc.

There are 26 different proposals that were successfully completed and the partner facilities provided a total of 31 different services, exceeding the 24 accesses initially expected. The final proposal is scheduled for September 2025. The summary of each proposal is shown in Annex IV

3.4. Feedback from the SMEs participants

To receive feedback from the SME beneficiaries of TamaTA-INNOV programme, a quick survey with 12 questions was sent using the link: <https://indico.cells.es/event/1613/>

It was sent to all the companies that completed the proposal and the answers were treated anonymously. The list of questions is:

1. How did you know about LEAPS-INNOV and in particular about the TamaTA-INNOV SME access programme?
2. Was it easy to submit a proposal?
3. Do you think that the procedure for this type of European Union funds is simple and easy for a SME?
4. Did you get valuable results from the experiment that you performed?
5. Have you used the results for developing an innovation or a patent? Was the innovation or patent related to a new material, product or service?
6. Did you find it useful to have chance to access to all the main European light sources through a single point of access?
7. Was it the first time that you used a light source infrastructure?
8. After this TamaTA-INNOV access, have you used a light source again? With or without the TamaTA-INNOV scheme?
9. Do you foresee to use a light source infrastructure again in the future?
10. Would you recommend TamaTA-INNOV access to other SMEs?

11. Would you suggest any changes to the current TamaTA-INNOV scheme?
12. Any other comment?

33% of the companies answered the survey and results can be summarised as follow:

- ✓ 100% found easy to submit a proposal
- ✓ 90% think that the overall procedure is simple and easy
- ✓ 90% obtained valuable results
- ✓ 33% was the first time using light sources
- ✓ 33% used a light source again
- ✓ 67% foresee using again light sources

In addition to these positive comments, the companies also made some recommendations that can be considered for future similar programmes:

- Larger projects are desirable (e.g., include sample preparation or additional support for the project)
- To have a clearer role or involvement of the facilities
- Do not limit to one application per company and project

In summary, SMEs confirm that the TamaTA-INNOV scheme is in general easy and useful and it is a very valuable tool to engage companies for the first time and increase the portfolio of companies that know the capabilities of light sources. In addition, the programme was helpful to show that results obtained with light sources are very valuable for industrial challenges. The recommendations made by the SMEs will also contribute to focus and improve future programmes and funding.

3.5. Case studies

A very interesting output from this programme is generating different case studies from the performed experiments illustrating the usefulness and the powerfulness of the analytical techniques available at light sources as well as the convenience of having industry programmes like TamaTA-INNOV. This material can also serve as an inspiration for other companies. In that regard, several case studies have been prepared:

CASE STUDY 1

CTC is using ALBA synchrotron for a better understanding of the efficacy of hair products

CTC (Centro de Tecnología Capilar) is a Spanish company specialised in personal hair and scalp care that has become an expert in the research and development of innovative technologies for assessing the efficacy of active ingredients and finished hair care products. The R&D activities of the company involve consultancy, formulation, efficacy test, training and advance technology solutions for the hair industry challenges. In that regard, CTC is continuously seeking for new and modern technologies to complement the studies and characterisation with non-conventional techniques such as the synchrotron light. In particular, the FTIR (Fourier Transform infrared) micro-spectroscopic imaging method available at ALBA synchrotron (MIRAS beamline) enables chemical imaging by combining spectral and spatial information. This technique allows characterising the internal parts of the hair and evaluate the effects of a damaging treatments in the biochemical components of the hair as well as the beneficial effects of a cosmetic product.

TamaTA-INNOV funding for SMEs is a very interesting tool for companies that would like to test the capabilities of light sources and to show them the valuable information that can be obtained. In this project, the company CTC had the opportunity to have access to MIRAS beamline at ALBA synchrotron and compare different hair samples through TamaTA-INNOV funding scheme. The goal of the study was to confirm the protective effect of a natural cosmetic product. This preliminary study showed some indications of changes in the samples that will need to be confirmed with further analysis.

These type of analysis and services require a strong relationship between the light source and the company to carefully plan the experiment and analyse the results, crucial steps for a successful project. For all this, TamaTA-INNOV is a very useful programme, easy and agile, that helping to get closer light source facilities to SME companies.

Figure 1. Hair cross section of a control sample showing the distribution of lipids (white and pink colours show the highest concentration of lipids and blue the lowest).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101004728

CASE STUDY 2

High-resolution synchrotron XRD analysis for damage-tolerant bearing steel

Bearings are exposed to cyclic loads during their operation. This causes deteriorations in the steel microstructure. The type of microstructural evolution ranges from stress-induced martensite transformation, formation of elongated ferrite and ferrite microbands, to the formation of white etching bands and lenticular cementite. The decay of the steel microstructure during cyclic loading also includes cementite dissolution and re-precipitation, and such phenomena are strongly dependent on dislocation rearrangement. These make dislocation density a critical parameter in affecting the microstructural evolution and, accordingly, the performance of a bearing.

However, the investigation of dislocation density evolution in the steel subsurface is limited at lab-scale X-ray diffraction devices (XRD) because of their large beam size. Furthermore, due to the low penetration depth only the near-surface information can be detected. This hinders the complete understanding of microstructural evolution that can pave the way for the design of better steel microstructure for more compact and lighter bearings.

Within the project, scientists from Scatterin AB teamed up with the global engineering steel producer Ovako AB for 2D mapping study of the dislocation density evolution in bearing steel subsurfaces. The synchrotron X-ray diffraction measurements were performed at the Swedish Materials Science Beamline P21.2 (SMS) at the Petra III, DESY in Hamburg, as part of the Tamata-Innov funded project in particular for SME. Whilst Ovako has contributed to the project by providing steel expertise, sample preparation, and complementary lab-scale investigations, Scatterin has been responsible for the synchrotron XRD measurements and data analysis using their dislocation density analysis code package as part of their software product ‘Scatterin SaaS’.

Synchrotron XRD has enabled an unprecedented spatial resolution in measurements within a significantly shorter measurement time. High-resolution monochromator, small beam size, and use of large area detectors revealed features and trends that are impossible to observe in a lab-based X-ray instruments. A significant number of measurements were performed within minutes, which would otherwise take days in lab measurement.

Figure 1. Dislocation density evolution in bearing steel subsurface revealed in μm resolution.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101004728

CASE STUDY 3

TamaTA- INNOV success story: AmaDema and ESRF

A concrete example of the TamaTA-INNOV impact for European SMEs, is the successful case of AmaDema, a small company based in Cyprus which focuses on the enhancement of technical fabrics and prepregs (laminated composites of fibre sheets that are impregnated with polymer resins) to be used in fibre-reinforced composites. AmaDema deals with the design and manufacturing of advanced composite materials, by identifying the problems and needs of customers in a variety of industries such as aviation, defence, sports, automotive, shipping, etc., and by providing them with a variety of services and products solutions in the field of materials.

AmaDema has introduced NanoWeld[®], a revolutionary, easily adjustable technology that significantly enhances the mechanical properties of fibre-reinforced polymer composites (FRPs), allowing the use of less material (fewer composite layers) to achieve the same load-bearing capacity. NanoWeld[®] technology increases composite performance by up to 100% for certain mechanical properties and reduces their weight by up to 15% compared to standard composites. NanoWeld[®] creates a hierarchical reinforcement at the damage-prone regions (interlayer), using nanofibres and protruding nanoparticles that work as anchors with the matrix, resulting in the increased mechanical performance of FRP composites.

Thanks to Tamata-Innov, AmaDema's had the opportunity to collaborate with ESRF, to expand AmaDema's understanding of the underlying mechanisms of NanoWeld[®] through the investigation of the various interfaces formed between the material phases. AmaDema will use these insights to better control the overall performance of the final product and strengthen its NanoWeld[®] portfolio.

<https://www.esrf.fr/home/Industry/industry-news/content-news/esrf-news-list/tamata-innov-boosting-the-smes-research-facilities-cooperation.html>

CASE STUDY 4

How Nanomol Technologies used the ALBA synchrotron to investigate new plant-based vesicular delivery systems

Nanomol Technologies is a GMP certified pharmaceutical laboratory delivering solutions to process, formulate and characterize, at micro and nanoscale, active molecules of pharma, biotech and healthcare companies. Their mission is to provide revolutionary nanomedicines and drug delivery systems with outstanding therapeutic efficacy and patient's compliance.

In their experiments at ALBA, Nanomol Technologies aimed to investigate, at the nanometre scale, a new platform of nanovesicles recently developed based on vegetal sterols and sugar-based surfactants using proprietary DELOS technology (EP patent filed in August 2022, besides granted procedure patents). These new vesicular delivery systems are composed of β -Sitosterol (Sit), Lauryl Glucoside (LGL) and Lauryl Glucose Carboxylate (LGC) molecules, all plant-based, biodegradable and biocompatible components. Nanomol used ALBA's small angle x-ray scattering (SAXS) beamline, NCD-SWEET, which can study structures in the 1-100 nm range. Here, analysis was performed to study the multi-lamellarity and cross-sectional structure of the nanovesicles, which allowed the characterization and classification of some promising formulations:

Figure 1 (left) shows SAXS data plotted in log-log scale, the experimental data as symbols and the model as continuous curves. Figure 2 (right) is Figure 1's legend, naming the relevant formulations.

The data collected at NCD-SWEET aided in the development of the new plant-based nanovesicles that can successfully function as topical delivery systems, with clear application in the pharmaceutical and healthcare industries (Alcaina-Hernando, M., et al. (2024). A new plant-based drug delivery platform based on alkyl polyglucosides and β -sitosterol nanovesicles for topical delivery. *Applied Materials Today*, 41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmt.2024.102467>). This investigation was made possible thanks to TamaTA-INNOV, a programme of the European project LEAPS-INNOV, which granted access to Nanomol Technologies to perform their studies at ALBA.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101004728

CASE STUDY 5

Scatterin Advances Composite Analysis with LEAPS-INNOV at DanMAX

Solid metals typically have their atoms arranged in a highly ordered crystalline structure that are aggregated to form a polycrystal. Carbon fibres, on the other hand, are only partially crystalline. Once amorphous epoxy is added to form a composite, the resulting structure is quite distinct from a metal with a very complex structure which lacks, to a large extent, long-range order of the atoms. Knowing more about this complex structure, specifically how each carbon fibre is aligned inside the composite, could allow engineers to tailor strength and stiffness to ultimately build lighter, safer products, including aeroplane components. Scatterin, a Swedish deep-tech company, has developed software that delivers live diffraction analysis at neutron and synchrotron beamlines, with a focus on metallic materials.

Through the TamaTA-INNOV access programme for SMEs (LEAPS-INNOV), Scatterin received beamtime at MAX IV's DanMAX beamline to study whether algorithms proven on metals could tackle carbon-fibre reinforced polymer components. At DanMAX's PXR instrument, the company was able to use a focused, size-tunable beam and a rapid sweep-mode stage that captured complete diffraction patterns from every angle in minutes. This was crucial to the success of the experiment.

The aim of this internal research was to achieve proof of concept that PXR measurements from DanMax, run through Scatterin's data analysis software, could reveal the orientation of individual fibres in semi-crystalline materials. "With these experiments at a synchrotron, we could map real components very quickly," Ahmet Bahadır Yıldız says. "We can then visualise at which part which fiber orientation we have."

With this proof of concept in hand, Scatterin is now looking ahead to industrial applications in technology ranging from aeroplanes to wind turbines. "This can increase innovation capacity, cut research and development cycles, and provide a powerful quality-control tool for industry," Yıldız adds.

Scatterin gratefully acknowledges the RISE Department of Polymer, Fibers and Composites for producing the reference components and for valuable discussions throughout the project. Scatterin would like to thank Mads Ry Jørgensen, Thorbjørn Erik Køppen Christensen, and Frederik Holm Gjørup of DanMAX for their support and excellent infrastructure. Part of this work was funded by the SMF Flyg programme under the National Aeronautical Research Programme (NFFP), Innovair, with joint funding from Vinnova and the Swedish Armed Forces.

Quote

LEAPS-INNOV enabled us to perform this proof of concept experiment on for us a new materials systems, carbon fibre-reinforced polymer, to validate if the methodology and the data analysis software and algorithms we use for metallic systems can be applied for this materials group. - Ahmet Bahadır Yıldız, CEO, Scatterin AB

Figure 1. X-ray diffraction patterns from three spots on the composite reveal distinct architectures: unidirectional, bidirectional and multidirectional fibres. Scatterin's software automatically identified the number and angles of dominant fibre directions in each area

Figure 2. The sample set-up at the beamline, with the three different fibre orientation zones marked.

CASE STUDY 6

The Protein Forge Ltd: Advancing Targeted Therapies with Protein Lattice Technology

Based in Oxford, UK, The Protein Forge Ltd is a biotech start-up pioneering proprietary protein-based technologies to develop innovative new therapies. Their engineered protein lattice systems are designed for use as a vaccine platform and for targeted drug delivery, selectively binding to specific cells to minimize side effects and enhance therapeutic efficacy.

By integrating advanced protein engineering with artificial intelligence, the team is pushing the boundaries of precision medicine. However, verifying the structural integrity of their protein lattices required access to macromolecular diffraction data—resources typically beyond the reach of a small start-up.

Support from the TamaTA-INNOV grant made this possible. It enabled access to the state-of-the-art facilities at Diamond Light Source, where expert staff assisted in preparing samples for high-resolution data collection. The resulting diffraction data confirmed that the engineered protein lattice matched the designed structure, validating the team's methodology and reinforcing the potential of their platform.

CASE STUDY 7

ESRF Supporting Renaissance Fusion's Stellarator Development

Background

In recent years, start-ups have pursued what has eluded multi-billion-dollar international projects: generating useful energy through nuclear fusion. Among these is Renaissance Fusion, a company established in 2020 in Grenoble, France, with the ambitious goal of developing an advanced stellarator - a complex magnetic confinement device for steady-state fusion energy. Unlike the more common tokamak, the stellarator uses twisted, helical magnetic fields to confine plasma, offering theoretical advantages such as continuous operation and reduced plasma instabilities. However, historically, stellarators have faced engineering challenges, including the need for highly complex, precisely aligned coils.

Innovation Challenge

Renaissance Fusion is tackling these challenges head-on, with innovations centred on high-temperature superconductors (HTS). Conventional HTS materials come in narrow 12 mm tapes, limiting their scalability and application. Renaissance Fusion aims to revolutionise this by developing one-metre-wide HTS sheets that can be laser-cut to custom shapes, similar to modern circuit manufacturing.

Realising this vision requires the design of large, sophisticated physical and chemical vapour deposition (PVD/CVD) machines, capable of achieving and maintaining excellent vacuum conditions - a key requirement for producing high-quality superconducting films at scale.

ESRF's Contribution

This is where the ESRF's expertise has played a pivotal role. Under the EU-funded TamaTA-INNOV synchrotron access programme, Renaissance Fusion has collaborated closely with ESRF's Vacuum Group, led by Cristian Maccarrone. The ESRF team has supported Renaissance Fusion with detailed calculations, measurements and vacuum system design guidance for three critical areas of development:

- New PVD/CVD machines
- A next-generation vacuum vessel
- A liquid-metals experiment essential for stellarator performance

Renaissance Fusion's Carlo Sborchia, head of magnets, vacuum, and cryogenics, highlights the value of this partnership: *"We don't have the vacuum expertise that Cristian has, so his contribution has been really valuable. We hope to continue collaborating with the ESRF as we advance our stellarator design."*

Broader Impact

The innovations emerging from this collaboration have the potential to transform not only fusion technology but also wider industries: large HTS sheets could simplify and reduce costs in HTS power cables and energy storage systems, opening new markets for superconducting technologies.

Domenico D'Andrea, Renaissance Fusion's head of business development and sales, sums up the partnership's significance: *"The ESRF is a very prestigious research centre, so it's great to be associated with it."*

Conclusion

This case study demonstrates how the ESRF's unique expertise and infrastructure can accelerate breakthrough technologies in emerging industries, supporting innovation far beyond traditional synchrotron science and helping visionary companies like Renaissance Fusion to realise transformative goals.

Figure 1: Stellarator developed at Renaissance Fusion (Credit: Renaissance <https://renfusion.eu/impact-business>)

CASE STUDY 8

Structural analysis of acrylic copolymer films at ALBA Synchrotron

ONYRIQ is a SME committed with science and R&D, expert on polymers, which offers a customised service based on innovative solutions to differentiate polymer based products from the market.

ONYRIQ is developing new coatings based on acrylic dispersions in water. The polymers are based on different acrylic monomers prepared by a radical emulsion polymerization process. Considering the complex composition of these polymers, **the elucidation of their structure is essential to improve the performance of the coatings** to meet the industrial requirements. Fundamental characterization does not provide enough information about the monomer distribution among the polymer chain thus, advanced characterization techniques, such as synchrotron techniques, are needed. In this project, **SAXS technique at the NCD-SWEET beamline, ALBA Synchrotron**, was used.

Thanks to the results obtained during this service, ONYRIQ is able to develop new materials with better performance and durability. Moreover, the materials present a sustainable alternative to the toxic fluorine compounds currently used, that will be soon banned in Europe market. In terms of durability, these types of coatings will avoid leaching of toxic substances to the environment, due to their complex structure linked to the substrate.

The knowledge obtained by these experiments carried out in ALBA Synchrotron will help ONYRIQ to design the coatings and to improve their properties, according to industrial requirements and to expand their current portfolio of products with a positive economic impact.

This investigation was made possible thanks to TamaTA-INNOV, a programme of the European Project LEAPS-INNOV, which granted access to Onyriq to perform their studies at the SAXS beamline, NCD-SWEET, ALBA Synchrotron.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101004728

Besides the case studies, a brochure was created, collecting several examples from TamaTA-INNOV but also including the previous pilot programme implemented in CALIPSOplus, named TamaTA. This document is addressed to SMEs but also stakeholders, industry associations and key partners to show the advantages of having these types of programmes and the outcome in a very simple and visual way. The document name is “The TamaTA programme presents: Why SMEs need Light Sources” and is published at: <https://zenodo.org/records/10137788>

3.6. Outreach activities and promotion material

A specific webpage page for all the partners was created in the wayforlight portal (Figure 13). The webpage provides concise information for the companies that wanted to apply and allowed them to understand in a quick and straightforward way what the TamaTA-INNOV programme was about and which were the contact points of the industrial liaison offices of each facility (<https://wayforlight.eu/en/industries/>).

Figure 13: Partial view of the industry page in wayforlight
(<https://wayforlight.eu/en/industries/>)

In addition, different materials were created to disseminate the programme within SMEs (A0 poster, A5 flyer and HTML file, Figure 14).

Figure 14: A5 flyer content

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Engaging SMEs is strategic for light sources but it is also particularly challenging. For this reason, the involvement of all LEAPS-INNOV partners has been crucial to enhance the awareness of light sources capabilities within the industries and to promote the TamaTA-INNOV programme. In that regard, many different activities have been carried out including dissemination on webpages, social media and participation and organisation of events focused on industrial needs. During the LEAPS-INNOV project, partners have participated in many different industry events, the most relevant are shown in Annex V. Partners participated in more than 90 different relevant events, both on-line and in person, at national and international levels, reaching more than 40.000 attendees involved in many different industrial sectors. Social media has also been used to disseminate the programme.

ALBA and the ESRF together with INESC, ELIXR and EuroBioimaging organised a workshop in Brussels, on June 7, 2024 “Enhancing SME Access to European Research and Technology Infrastructures: A Pathway to Innovation & Growth”. This event brought together over 40 participants, including SME associations, industry representatives, policymakers, funders, and major European RTIs. The objective was to address the barriers SMEs face in utilising RTIs and to develop strategies for enhancing collaboration between SMEs and RTIs. The workshop underscored the importance of cohesive strategies and supportive policies to enhance SME access to RTIs. Addressing the identified challenges and leveraging opportunities can create a more inclusive and innovative ecosystem, driving European competitiveness and sustainability.

<https://sciencebusiness.net/network-updates/enhancing-sme-access-european-research-and-technology-infrastructures>

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101004728

3.7. Conclusions of TamaTA-INNOV and long-term perspectives

A unified access programme for SMEs, named TamaTA-INNOV, was established, building on the experience of a previous pilot initiative. This programme featured an agile, straightforward, and user-friendly process. Four calls for proposals were launched. Thanks to targeted outreach efforts at each facility, 32 unique proposals were received, requesting access to 38 different services, 31 of which have been successfully completed, exceeding the 24 accesses initially expected.

The single entry point mechanism enabled companies to access multiple facilities simultaneously within the same project, allowing for a more comprehensive and integrated service. This approach has proven highly beneficial in several cases, improving both the quality and complementarity of services offered by light sources.

SMEs have reported that the TamaTA-INNOV scheme was easy and highly useful. It served as a valuable gateway for first-time engagement and helped expand the portfolio of companies familiar with the advanced capabilities of light sources. Moreover, the programme has demonstrated that results obtained through light sources can effectively address industrial challenges. Participating companies have recommended increasing project sizes and introducing greater flexibility.

In conclusion, the combination of dedicated funding and a single entry point for SMEs has proven to be an effective tool for fostering innovation across European companies. Extending the programme with long-term support and increased funding would further strengthen and sustain the connection between light sources and SMEs.

4. General conclusions on innovation activities and future recommendations

The LEAPS-INNOV project has demonstrated that European light source are powerful innovation enablers for industry, particularly SMEs. Through coordinated efforts in Work Package 8, the project successfully **engaged with almost 90 different companies in total**, most of them SMEs and advanced two complementary goals:

1. Exploitation of Technology Results (Task 8.1.1):

A structured approach involving 56 industrial partners (nearly half of them SMEs) ensured practical application of technological developments across six technical work packages. Industry was integrated through tenders, co-development, and early collaboration. While engagement was strong, gaps in

intellectual property management, standardisation, and procurement complexities were highlighted as barriers to smoother partnerships.

2. **Support for SMEs via TamaTA-INNOV (Task 8.2):**

The subsidised access programme enabled 32 projects from SMEs from 14 countries to engage with light sources using a simplified single-entry point. Participating companies reported valuable outcomes, including increased TRLs, innovation generation, and strengthened interest in future collaboration. The initiative demonstrated the feasibility, value, and scalability of such schemes, especially when supported by clear communication, flexible procedures, and targeted outreach.

The LEAPS-INNOV experience confirms that light sources can serve as a bridge between scientific excellence and industrial innovation, but sustained support mechanisms and improved frameworks are needed to scale impact.

Suggested future steps

To deepen and sustain engagement between light sources and industry (especially SMEs) and based on the experience of LEAPS-INNOV the following actions are recommended:

1. Establish long-term access programmes and pilot new funding instruments
Transition TamaTA-INNOV into a permanent, EU-backed scheme with increased funding, flexible formats and rolling calls. In addition, explore co-funding mechanisms with national agencies and industrial consortia to support joint R&D projects or commercial upscaling of RI-derived innovations.
2. Strengthen IP and tech transfer support:
Embed Industrial Contact Officers (ICOs) into technical developments from very initial stages of developments to guide IP strategy, legal clarity, and exploitation planning.
3. Develop joint industry–RI roadmaps:
Co-create specific roadmaps aligning industrial needs with RI capabilities (e.g., in energy, materials, health), allowing for predictable, strategic collaboration.
4. Improve standardisation and qualification processes:
Harmonise metrology protocols, validation criteria, and procurement models across facilities to make them more accessible and predictable for industry partners.
5. Enhance outreach and marketing activities:
Use dedicated communication teams and digital platforms to continuously

promote capabilities, success stories, and co-development opportunities. Invest in industry-oriented events, training, and matchmaking.

6. Foster multi-facility, multi-service offerings:

Expand the single-entry point model to offer bundled, cross-facility services that leverage complementary strengths of light sources enabling more comprehensive industrial solutions.

Annex I - List of Companies involved in the technical workpackages

Company	Size (linkedin source)	Country
Allectra GmbH	SME	GERMANY
Ametek	SME	EUROPEAN
Ansaldo Energia	LARGE	ITALY
Arnold Magnetic Technologies AG	LARGE	SWITZERLAND
AVS - Added Value Solution	LARGE	SPAIN
Axilon AG	SME	SWITZERLAND
Bakerhicks	LARGE	EUROPEAN
Belcan	LARGE	POLAND
Bertin - Winlight	SME	FRANCE
Bruker Switzerland	LARGE	SWITZERLAND
Bruker/XG Labs	LARGE	ITALY
Can Superconductors	SME	CHECK REPUBLIC
Dectris	LARGE	SWITZERLAND
Vacuumschmelze GmbH & Co KGSEF	LARGE	GERMANY
Teledyne	LARGE	FRANCE
SmarAct GmbH	LARGE	GERMANY
Cecom Srl	LARGE	ITALY
EPOWERSYS	LARGE	SPAIN
Ewcon R&D Sweden AB	SME	SWEDEN
Huawei Technologies	LARGE	EUROPEAN
IBM	LARGE	EUROPEAN
Kyma	SME	ITALY
MDC Max Daetwyler	SME	SWITZERLAND
MI-Partners	SME	NETHERLANDS
Microlight3D	SME	FRANCE
Mirion Technologies	LARGE	EUROPEAN
Neomax Engineering Co. Ltd	SME	UK
NOB Nano Optics Berlin	SME	GERMANY
Philipps Innovation Services	LARGE	NETHERLANDS
Quantum detectors	SME	UK
Qutools GmbH	SME	GERMANY
Raith BV	LARGE	NETHERLANDS
RI Research Instruments GmbH	LARGE	GERMANY
SAES Getters Spa	LARGE	ITALY
SAFRAN - REOSC	LARGE	FRANCE
SEF - TECHNOLOGIES	SME	SPAIN
SENIS AG	SME	SWITZERLAND
T.E.E.S. Srl	SME	ITALY
Thales - SESO	LARGE	FRANCE
THEVA	LARGE	GERMANY
Txproducts	SME	GERMANY
UHV Design Ltd	SME	UK
XR Nanotech	SME	SWITZERLAND
X-Spectrum	SME	GERMANY
IronArray	SME	SPAIN
Nortemecanica S.A.	SME	SPAIN
Fagor Automation	LARGE	SPAIN
Safran N&T	LARGE	FRANCE
TRUMPF Hüttinger GmbH + Co. KG	LARGE	GERMANY

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SIGMAPHI	LARGE	FRANCE
ASG Superconductors Spa	LARGE	ITALY
Jema SA	LARGE	BELGIUM
Galvano - T	SME	GERMANY

Annex II. Terms of Reference for TamaTA-INNOV

The SME companies applying for industrial access to LEAPS-INNOV (TamaTA-INNOV) will be required to accept the following

1. Companies considered as SMEs according to EU definition: (https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes/sme-definition_en) and based on the EU, associated countries or third countries (up to a cumulative access of 20% of the total amount of units of access) can request access to the facilities participating in TamaTA-INNOV.
2. The access to TamaTA-INNOV facilities will be based on the submission of a proposal by the company during specific Calls for proposals opened through the single entry portal by TamaTA-INNOV coordinators.
3. The industrial proposals should be submitted via <http://www.wayforlight.eu> and should contain the information requested, in particular, the project research description, the type of samples to be measured, the innovation, the potential impact and the preferred light sources.
4. Prior to proposal submission it is strongly recommended that the SME consults with the facilities.
5. Only one proposal per company and per Call will be accepted. If the proposal is rejected, it can be rewritten and resubmitted during the same Call for proposals. A SME can only submit one proposal per topic to all the Calls except in very well justified cases.
6. An independent Panel of Experts will evaluate the proposals according to the established evaluation criteria which will determine the selected proposals.
7. The evaluation criteria are based on the scientific merit, on the product or service innovation and on the potential impact of the proposal.
8. The proposal evaluation will be performed on a continuous basis to minimize the response time to the companies.
9. The selected proposals will preferentially be assigned to the preferred facility stated on the proposal and it does not in any way imply a commitment or obligation on the part of the LEAPS-INNOV or the facility. LEAPS-INNOV reserves the right to assign a facility different from the company preference according to feasibility checks and light source internal rules.
10. The SME and the facility will discuss the proposal details for an optimum experiment design. A non-disclosure agreement can be signed between the company and the light-source facility if required.
11. An access form will be issued by the facility considering the time estimation to carry out the experiments and works of the proposal. It must be signed by both the facility and the SME. The costs of providing the service will be covered by LEAPS-INNOV and the beamtime costs will be covered by the facility as an in-kind contribution or invoiced depending on each partner's legal requirements. The

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provision for access will not cover any other costs related to the works such as shipment of the samples to the light source. It does not preclude the need to follow other formalities required by the facility.

12. The experiment will be carried out based in a mail-in or remote procedure with no physical presence of the industrial researchers. The company will mail-in the sample(s) in a timely manner and in accordance with instructions from the facility.

13. The experiments and work will be carried out following the access rules of the facilities. Refusal to follow those regulations may imply the termination of the service.

14. At the conclusion of the experiment the company will receive a report containing the information agreed between the company and the facility.

15. The information of the proposal and experiment will be treated as confidential. Due to the industrial nature of the experiment performed, the experiment results obtained at the facilities under the present LEAPS-INNOV access and communicated to the SME by the facility shall be owned by the SME and no publication of the results is required. However, as the works performed are supported by the LEAPS-INNOV project which is funded by the European Union, the companies shall grant the TamaTA-INNOV facilities the right to disseminate their names, a short background of the company and a brief summary of the performed experiment, without confidential information, for reporting purpose to the European Commission and to other related institutions.

16. The processing of the personal data is subject to the provisions of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and other applicable regulations. The personal data forms part of a file responsibility of ALBA Synchrotron as co-leaders of the TamaTA-INNOV; the Data Protection Officer (DPO) can be contacted at the following e-mail address dpd@cells.es.

17. By submitting a proposal application under TamaTA-INNOV, the company agrees to the present Terms and Conditions and confirms and certifies that all information provided to LEAPS-INNOV is true and accurate, and that they undertake to respect all LEAPS-INNOV, European Union and national rules and regulations.

Annex III: TamaTA-INNOV documents

EVALUATION REPORT

Confidential

Proposal ID	
Title	

Criterion	Score
Scientific merit (0-5)	
Innovation (0-5)	
Potential impact (0-5)	

<i>To include a short explanation supporting your scores is required</i>

I, the undersigned, hereby declare:

- that I do not have any conflict of interest in connection with the present evaluation.
- that I will keep confidential all the information and content of the evaluated proposal.

Signature

Name:

Place and date:

ACCESS FORM

Proposal ID	
Title	
SME name	
Facility name	

Service	Amount	Comments	Supported/invoiced/in-kind (select all that apply)
Beamtime provision (h)			i.e. Invoiced or in-kind
Data analysis (h)			Supported by LEAPS-INNOV
Sample preparation (h)			Supported by LEAPS-INNOV
Others (please, specify)			i.e. Supported by LEAPS-INNOV

- The present provision of access proposal expires at the end date of the LEAPS-INNOV project.
- The access to the facility shall be performed according to the Terms of Reference accepted when the proposal was submitted. Among them it is worthwhile noticing that the access is supported by the LEAPS-INNOV project (TamaTA-INNOV) funded by the EU's H2020 research and innovation programme.

Facility signature	Company signature
Name:	Name:
Position:	Position:
Place and date:	Place and date:

ACCESS FORM-JOINT SERVICES

Proposal ID	
Title	
SME name	
Facility names	

Service	Facility	Amount	Comments	Supported/invoiced/in-kind (select all that apply)
Beamtime provision (h)				i.e. Invoiced or in-kind
Data analysis (h)				Supported by LEAPS-INNOV
Sample preparation (h)				Supported by LEAPS-INNOV
Others (please, specify)				i.e. Supported by LEAPS-INNOV

- The present provision of access proposal expires at the end date of the LEAPS-INNOV project.
- The access to the facility shall be performed according to the Terms of Reference accepted when the proposal was submitted. Among them it is worthwhile noticing that the access is supported by the LEAPS-INNOV project (TamaTA-INNOV) funded by the EU's H2020 research and innovation programme.

Facility signature	Facility signature	Company signature
Name:	Name:	Name:
Position:	Position:	Position:
Place and date:	Place and date:	Place and date:

ACCESS REPORT

Proposal ID	
Title	
SME name	
Facility name	

Work and results summary (no confidential information)	
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Service	Date of service	Amount	Comments	Supported/invoiced/in-kind (select all that apply)
Beamtime provision (h)				i.e. Invoiced or in-kind
Data analysis (h)				Supported by LEAPS-INNOV
Sample preparation (h)				Supported by LEAPS-INNOV
Others (please, specify)				i.e. Supported by LEAPS-INNOV

Comments	
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Facility signature
Name:
Position:
Place and date:

ACCESS REPORT-JOINT SERVICES

Proposal ID	
Title	
SME name	
Facility names	

Work and results summary (no confidential information)	
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Service	Facility	Date of service	Amount	Comments	Supported/invoiced/in-kind (select all that apply)
Beamtime provision (h)					i.e. Invoiced or in-kind
Data analysis (h)					Supported by LEAPS-INNOV
Sample preparation (h)					Supported by LEAPS-INNOV
Others (please, specify)					i.e. Supported by LEAPS-INNOV

Comments	
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Facility signature	Facility signature
Name:	Name:
Position:	Position:
Place and date:	Place and date:

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Annex IV. Summary of the SME proposals received through TamaTA-INNOV

Call	Proposal ID	SME	Title	Facility selected	Feasibility Check	External Review	Status
1	TamaTA-INNOV-20220330-0821-CBCC	Orbital Express Launch ApS	Quality control of Additive Manufactured rocket engine parts	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	complete
1	TamaTA-INNOV-20220614-1234-FB19	MPP SRL (Belgium)	TOMOGRAPHY OF NEW HIGH DENSITY INCONEL 3D PRINTED PARTS	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	Cancelled: The client decided to not continue with the experiment
1	TamaTA-INNOV-20220615-1006-55B9	Imagine Optic	Differentiate samples through measurement of optical index (delta, beta) in the 5-25 keV energy range	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	complete
1	TamaTA-INNOV-20220620-0646-FCFD	CTC	Hair and Scalp Solutions for protein protection	ALBA	Accepted	Accepted	complete
1	TamaTA-INNOV-20220620-1646-A903	Scatterin AB	Mapping dislocation density evolution in bearing steel subsurface using synchrotron X-ray diffraction	DESY	Accepted	Accepted	complete
1	TamaTA-INNOV-20220704-0835-67D6	Francesco Pellisari	The relationship between residual strain and sound transmission in earthenware components, employed by the Hi-Fi industry	ESRF	Accepted with changes accepted by the company	Accepted	complete
1	TamaTA-INNOV-20220713-1447-A898	AmaDema - Advanced Materials Design & Manufacturing Limited	Investigation of the multiscale structure of NanoWeld® carbon fiber reinforced composites	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	complete
1	TamaTA-INNOV-20220728-1600-439F	IMcoMET B.V.	Determining the effect of local soluble microenvironment flushing with M-Duo microneedles on collagen hydrogel nanostructure using Small Angle X-Ray Scattering (SAXS)	ALBA	Accepted	Accepted	complete
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20220925-1658-A39D	Excelsus Structural Solutions (Swiss) AG	Enhancement of the accuracy of quantification of small fractions of crystalline Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (APIs)	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	Additional facility formalised (SOLEIL).complete
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20220929-0733-DOCE	Tec Eurolab Srl	Multi materials components by hybrid 3D Printing manufacturing	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	complete
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20221028-0721-D246	Provital S.A.	Global protection of Provital product on structural integrity of hair shafts	ALBA	Accepted	Accepted	complete
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20221205-0846-AD98	Nanomol Technologies	SAXS characterization of novel nanovesicles for drug delivery	ALBA	Accepted	Accepted	complete

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2	TamaTA-INNOV-20230203-1032-931A	Iconovo AB	High speed X-ray radiography of nasal inhaler	MAXIV, ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	complete
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20230213-1813-309F	Nanoramic Laboratories	Development of High Capacity “High Power and longevity Li-ion batteries	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	complete
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20230220-0930-0E2E	Renaissance Fusion SAS	Vacuum characterization of materials for fusion reactor design	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	complete
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20230301-1252-B995	The Protein Forge Ltd.	Crystalline therapeutics	Diamond	Accepted	Accepted	Complete
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20230419-1216-C6A1	Officine Ambrogio Melesi & C s.r.l.	Detection of alpha prime ferritic phase in forged and heat treated 2205 duplex stainless steel	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	Discarded, not SME
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20230519-0748-331A	Scatterin AB	Quantification of residual stresses in complex aero engine parts: demonstration and validation measurements	DESY	Accepted	Accepted	complete
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20230724-0932-24CB	Evolgene Genomics S.L	Wet-spinning induced orientation of cellulose based fibers for renewable textiles	ALBA	Accepted	Accepted	complete
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20230724-1325-6DB4	Silson Ltd	A Novel Platform for Direct-bandgap Group-IV Semiconductors for Photonics Applications	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	complete
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20230726-0801-216F	CONIFY SMPC	AMAC++	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	complete
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20230726-0903-5A32	3D-COMPONENTS AS	AMRES+	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	Service no longer available at ESRF (not performed)
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20230727-1020-3CE9	Demus SpA	Improvement of the decaffeination production process	ELETTRA	Accepted	Accepted	complete
2	TamaTA-INNOV-20230728-1207-1343	ReActive - Powder Technology s.r.l.	Production of innovative materials by resonance high energy mechanical activation	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	complete
3	TamaTA-INNOV-20231026-1024-6991	Discauton Ltd	Ultrashort Pulsed Laser Imaging Validation With Correlative uXCT to Unlock Semiconductor Productivity	ESRF	Accepted	Not Accepted	Discarded, not granted
3	TamaTA-INNOV-20240109-1101-F698	ONYRIQ LABS SL	Structural analysis of acrylic copolymer films (using GISAXS)	ALBA	Accepted	Accepted	complete
3	TamaTA-INNOV-20240227-0823-B991.pdf	Accelerated Muscle Biotechnologies LLC (AMB)	Developing skeletal and cardiac muscle applications at the NCD-SWEET beamline for academic and industrial use	ALBA	Accepted	Accepted	complete
3	TamaTA-INNOV-20240711-0835-E8C8.pdf	Scatterin AB	Proof-of-concept synchrotron XRD measurements on composites	MAXIV	Accepted	Accepted	complete
3	TamaTA-INNOV-20240719-1241-F524.pdf	Blackwave GmbH	Measurement of Fiber Orientation in Carbon Sheet Molding Compound Specimens Using Synchrotron X-ray Tomography	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	complete

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3	TamaTA-INNOV-20240724-1243-0A93.pdf	Instituto de Investigación Biotecnológica, Farmacéutica y Medicamentos Huérfanos, S.L.	Studies of Epidermal Growth Factor (EGF) activity in fibroblast cells	ALBA	Accepted	Accepted	complete
3	TamaTA-INNOV-20240724-1446-6E1D	NOVITOM	In-situ compressive μ -CT of additive manufactured lattice structures with negative effective Poisson's ratios and their comparison with a metallic foam	ESRF	Accepted	Accepted	Not performed (Late delivery of samples)
4	TamaTA-INNOV-20250529-0802-855F.pdf	AMPHOS 21 CONSULTING S.L.	Identification of Secondary Mineral Phases in Quartz-Rich sands Exposed to Cement Plumes at the CSA Radioactive Waste Repository	ALBA	ongoing	Accepted	ongoing

Annex V. List of events in which the different partners have participated and publications

Event	Date	Place	Estimated number of attendees
Industrial applications of ALBA Synchrotron in cements, pigments and ceramics	19/05/2021	Zoom, online	40
SPRING Paris-Saclay 2021	20/05/2021	Online	1800
CONNEXT 2020 presso il MiCo - Milano Convention Center	06/2021	Milano convention center	10
ConneXions R&D Cosmetic Valley 2021	08/06/2021	Online	50
Nanoinnovation 2021	09/2021	Zoom, online	5
Expoquimia	15/09/2021	Barcelona	20
Meetin Italyforlifescience 2021	10/2021	Zoom, online	15
Visit of SOLEIL by the AMI association	10/2021	Saint-Aubin, France	20
COSMETIC 360 (International Innovation Fair for Cosmetics Industry) 2021	13&14/10/2021	Paris, France	5000
Cosmetorium 2021	21/10/2021	Barcelona	20
Visit of SOLEIL by the company Saint-Gobain Cristaux et Détecteurs	27/10/2021	Saint-Aubin, France	12
Business convention Rendez-vous Carnot 2021	17&18/11/2021	Lyon, France	1900
Cosmetic Visit R&D Cosmetomics Ile-de-France	23/11/2021	Cergy-Pontoise, France	50
Hangar 21, Tech show	30/11/2021	Secpho platform, online	30
Industrial Application of Elettra Synchrotron for pharmaceuticals companies	12/2021	Modena, DEMOCENTER	20
Webinar TamaTA: subsidised measurements for SMEs at ALBA Synchrotron	02/12/2021	Zoom, online	25
Oppurtunies for business @ Elettra Synchrotron	01/2022	Zoom, online	40
Business Photonics Meeting Environnement	15/02/2022	Paris, France	30
Business convention TechInnov 2022	23/03/2022	Paris, France	2000
Visit of SOLEIL by a delegation of the France Bioproduction Congress	06/04/2022	Saint-Aubin, France	15
SPRING Paris-Saclay 2022	12&13/05/2022	Palaiseau, France	1800
Visit of SOLEIL by the cluster EMS (Eau-Milieu-Sols)	17/05/2022	Saint-Aubin, France	25
Business Photonics Meeting Agroalimentaire	24/05/2022	Paris, France	50
Smart Agrifood Industry	25-26/05/2022	Secpho platform, online	40
MECSPE Bologna	06/2022	Bologna Trade Fair	50
Industrial applications of ALBA Synchrotron for the pharmaceutical industry	17/06/2022	ALBA Synchrotron, Cerdanyola del Valles	50
COMET (International Congress for Testing & Measurement in Cosmetics) 2022	05&06/07/2022	Cergy-Pontoise, France	200
AWT - FA 13 Eigenspannungen (Residual Stresses)	19.-20/07/2022	Hannover	120
How to innovate with ALBA Synchrotron	14/09/2022	Secpho platform, online	8
Industry collaboration: MaxLab IV & ESS & Alfa Laval & Swedish Research Council	19.&20/09/2022	PSI, Villigen, Switzerland	20
ALBA Synchrotron: a tool to innovate in the Health sector	20/09/2022	Scientific Parc of Barcelona	20

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Cosmetorium 2022	27/09/2022	Barcelona	20
Meetin Italyforlifescience 2022	10/2022	Zoom, online	7
COSMETIC 360 (International Innovation Fair for Cosmetics Industry) 2022	12&13/10/2022	Paris, France	5000
Business convention Rendez-vous Carnot 2022	12&13/10/2022	Paris, France	2000
CPHI Frankfurt	11/2022	Frankfurt Messe	15
ProRA 2022 (process-related X-ray analysis)	24.-25.11.2022	Berlin	120
Advanced Microscopy	10/12/2022	Secpho platform, online	25
Webinar ALBA synchrotron: high technology for industries	16/12/2022	Zoom, online	20
Batterieforum Deutschland	18.-20.01.2023	Berlin	300
Harwell large scale RI supplier info day	11/03/2023	Harwell	30
Visit of SOLEIL by the company Porsche Consulting	24/03/2023	Saint-Aubin, France	25
Innovation workshop for cosmetics and fragrances	04/05/2023	online	15
IPAC 2023	04/05/2023	Venice	1600
SPRING Paris-Saclay 2023	01&02/06/2023	HEC, Jouy-en-Josas, France	1800
Visit of SOLEIL by the a japanese delegation of Sendai City & Japan Embassy in Paris	14/06/2023	Saint-Aubin, France	6
Visit of SOLEIL by the Danone Research & Innovation Center	14/09/2023	Saint-Aubin, France	3
Visit of SOLEIL by the Servier Paris-Saclay Center	28/09/2023	Saint-Aubin, France	18
Visit of SOLEIL by the Renault Technocenter	29/09/2023	Saint-Aubin, France	30
Visit of SOLEIL by a delegation of Innovation Directors of Luxembourg	12/10/2023	Saint-Aubin, France	8
Business convention Rendez-vous Carnot 2023	18&19/10/2023	Lyon, France	2000
COSMETIC 360 (International Innovation Fair for Cosmetics Industry) 2023	18&19/10/2023	Paris, France	5000
Paints and Coatings 2023	14/11/2023	Barcelona	20
Visit of SOLEIL by the participants of the Global Energy Transition 2023 (GET 2023) Conference	14/11/2023	Saint-Aubin, France	12
Nordic Big Science industry days	14/11/2023	Copenhagen	20
The TamaTA Programme Present: Why SMEs Need Light Sources: Advanced Composites, Food Safety, Recycled Rubber and More	15/11/2023	N/A	1000
Slovak Industry Vision Day	23/11/2023	Samorin	150
Industry opportunities in light source infrastructures	01/12/2023	ALBA Synchrotron, Cerdanyola del Valles	120
Impact on Industry	01/01/2024	N/A	2000
Big Science Poland	12/01/2024	Krakow	160
Swedish Big Science Forum 2024	31/01/2024	Lund	30
Plastic & Rubber 2024	07/03/2024	Barcelona	15
BSBF satellite roadshow in Slovakia	22/03/2024	Bratislava	40
Circular economy day at SOLEIL	28/03/2024	Saint-Aubin, France	16
Belgian RI EU Presidency Conference	04/05/2024	Brussels	300
Enhancing SME Access to European Research and Technology Infrastructures	07/06/2024	Brussels	50

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Visits of SOLEIL by the company Saint-Gobain Research	21/08 & 12/11/2024	Saint-Aubin, France	13
BSBF2024	1-4/10/2024	Trieste	1000
COSMETIC 360 (International Innovation Fair for Cosmetics Industry) 2024	16&17/10/2024	Paris, France	5500
Visit of SOLEIL by a delegation of the Japan Economic Research Institute (JERI)	28/10/2024	Saint-Aubin, France	6
Big Science and Nomaten Innovation Day	19/11/2024	Warsaw	30
Paints and Coatings 2024	20/11/2024	Barcelona	15
Cosmetorium 2024	21/11/2024	Barcelona	25
COMET (International Congress for Testing & Measurement in Cosmetics) 2025	22&23/01/2025	Cergy-Pontoise, France	200
Plastic & Rubber 2025	13/03/2025	Barcelona	20
Visits of SMEs associations: Synchrotron light for SMEs	24/03/2025, 11/04/2025, 30/05/2025	ALBA Synchrotron, Cerdanyola del Valles	50
Belgian ILO and industry visit to ESRF	22/04/2025	Grenoble	20
Analysis workshop of the company TotalEnergies	20/05/2025	Chantilly, France	100
SPRING Paris-Saclay 2025	20&21/05/2025	Ecole Polytechnique, Palaiseau, France	1800
Synchrotron Imaging of materials for Industry Conference	21/05/2025	MinesParis, Paris, France	90
Industrial Opportunity Days	11/06/2025	Torino	100
CTLS2025	12/06/2025	Brno	
Visit of SOLEIL by the Servier Paris-Saclay Center	18/06/2025	Saint-Aubin, France	16
Cosmetic Valley Connexions 2025	19/06/2025	Béville-le-Comte, France	300

Relevant publications

Supporting European SMEs with smart access to research infrastructures:
Experience from three European projects

<https://zenodo.org/records/15447982>

The TamaTA Programme Present: Why SMEs Need Light Sources: Advanced Composites, Food Safety, Recycled Rubber and More

<https://zenodo.org/records/10137788>

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Social media publications:

<https://www.cells.es/en/media/news/new-call-for-smes-to-ask-for-funded-access-to-european-lightsources>

<https://twitter.com/ALBA synchrotron/status/1469291559606800385>

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6875056139348795392/>

<https://www.leaps-innov.eu/post/new-opportunities-for-smes-fundet-access-to-european-light-sources>

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<https://leaps-initiative.eu/new-opportunities-for-smes/>

<https://journals.iucr.org/s/issues/2023/01/00/s230100psi.pdf>

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https://www.linkedin.com/posts/elettra-sincrotrone-trieste tamata-innov-to-boost-innovation-in-european-activity-6985965723818856448-L1Cn?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

<https://www.elettra.eu/comunicazione/news/1-new-call-for-smes-to-ask-for-funded-access-to-european-lightsources.html>

https://www.helmholtz-berlin.de/industrie/index_en.html

<https://www.linkedin.com/posts/albasynchrotron sme-brussels-activity-7205833380603604993-7Mno/>

